

D5.3 Manual for UPJS staff (How to write a successful proposal for EU project)

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern Slovakia (CasProt)**

No. 952333

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is a short manual for UPJS staff containing advice and tips on how to write a successful proposal in the program Horizon Europe. It describes what the individual parts (Excellence, Impact, Implementation) of the proposal should contain.

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Chapter 1. GENERAL OVERVIEW

Writing a successful proposal for Horizon Europe, the European Union's flagship research and innovation funding program, requires careful planning, attention to detail, and adherence to specific guidelines. Here's a step-by-step guide to help you craft a compelling proposal:

1. Understand the Horizon Europe Program:

- Start by thoroughly reading the official Horizon Europe Work Programme relevant to your research area.
- Familiarize yourself with the specific call topics, evaluation criteria, and budget allocation for your chosen call.

2. Assemble Your Consortium:

- Identify and engage with potential partners, including academic institutions, research organizations, and industry partners, to form a strong consortium.
- Ensure each partner brings valuable expertise and resources to the project.

3. Develop a Clear and Innovative Concept:

- Clearly define the objectives, scope, and expected outcomes of your research project.
- Highlight the novelty and innovation of your proposal and how it addresses the specific challenges outlined in the call.

4. Address Evaluation Criteria:

- Carefully review the evaluation criteria provided in the call documentation.
- Ensure that your proposal addresses each criterion, including scientific excellence, impact, quality, and efficiency of implementation.

5. Work Plan and Methodology:

- Outline a detailed work plan, including tasks, milestones, and deliverables.
- Describe the research methodology, experimental design, and data analysis techniques.
- Clearly define the roles and responsibilities of each consortium member.

6. Impact and Dissemination:

- Highlight the expected impact of your project, including societal, economic, and policy relevance.
- Explain how you plan to disseminate and exploit project results, ensuring broad societal and industry engagement.

7. Budget and Resources:

- Develop a realistic budget that aligns with the project's objectives and activities.
- Justify your budget by explaining how it supports the project's goals.
- Ensure financial sustainability throughout the project's duration.

8. Ethical and Regulatory Compliance:

- Address any ethical considerations, data protection, and regulatory issues related to your research.
- Describe how you will manage these aspects to ensure compliance.

9. Write Clearly and Concisely:

- Use clear and concise language to communicate your ideas.
- Proofread and edit your proposal for clarity, coherence, and correctness.

10. Review and Feedback:

- Seek feedback from peers, mentors, or experts in your field to improve the quality of your proposal.
- Review your proposal against the evaluation criteria to ensure all aspects are adequately addressed.

11. Submit Your Proposal:

- Follow the submission guidelines provided in the Horizon Europe Work Programme.
- Submit your proposal by the specified deadline.

12. Prepare for Evaluation:

- Be prepared for the evaluation process, which may involve peer review and interviews.
- Address any clarifications or additional information requested by the evaluators promptly.

Remember that Horizon Europe is highly competitive, so it's crucial to make your proposal stand out by showcasing the excellence of your research, its potential impact, and your consortium's capabilities. Additionally, always ensure compliance with the specific guidelines and requirements outlined in the call for proposals.

Chapter 2. STRUCTURE OF THE PROPOSAL

Structure of the Proposal The proposal contains two parts:

- Part A of the proposal is generated by the IT system. It is based on the information entered by the participants through the submission system in the Funding & Tenders Portal. The participants can update the information in the submission system at any time before final submission.
- Part B of the proposal is the narrative part that includes three sections that each correspond to an evaluation criterion. Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the templates downloaded by the applicants in the submission system for the specific call or topic. The templates for a specific call may slightly differ from the example provided in this document.

The electronic submission system is an online wizard that guides you step-by-step through the preparation of your proposal.

The submission process consists of 6 steps:

- Step 1: Logging in the Portal
- Step 2: Select the call, topic and type of action in the Portal
- Step 3: Create a draft proposal: Title, acronym, summary, main organisation and contact details
- Step 4: Manage your parties and contact details: add your partner organisations and contact details.
- Step 5: Edit and complete web forms for proposal part A and upload proposal part B
- Step 6: Submit the proposal

Chapter 3. Proposal Part A

Abstract + Keywords

Abstracts should include a short introduction or background to put the research into context; purpose of the research project; a problem statement or thesis; a brief description of materials, methods, or subjects (as appropriate for the discipline); results and analysis; conclusions and implications; and recommendations.

Chapter 4. Proposal Part B

1. Title of the proposal

From template:

Fill in the title of your proposal below.

TITLE OF THE PROPOSAL

Our recommendation:

Make sure that the title is interesting and there is no other project with the same title. The same applies to the project acronym.

2. Consortium members

From template:

The consortium members are listed in part A of the proposal (application forms). A summary list should also be provided in the table below.

Participant No. *	Participant organisation name	Country
1 (Coordinator)		
2		
3		

* Please use the same participant numbering and name as that used in the administrative proposal forms.

Our recommendation:

Use the same participant numbering and name as that used in the administrative proposal form (part A).

Do not forget acronym of institution.

3. Excellence

From template:

Excellence – aspects to be taken into account.

- Clarity and pertinence of the project's objectives, and the extent to which the proposed work is ambitious, and goes beyond the state of the art.
- Soundness of the proposed methodology, including the underlying concepts, models, assumptions, interdisciplinary approaches, appropriate consideration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content, and the quality of open science practices, including sharing and management of research outputs and engagement of citizens, civil society and end users where appropriate.

The following aspects will be taken into account only to the extent that the proposed work is within the scope of the work programme topic.

Our recommendations:

This section serves as the gateway for applicants to leave a lasting impression on the evaluators. If an applicant manages to captivate the evaluators, their chances of success increase significantly. The introduction to the excellence section should address fundamental questions: "What" is the problem the project aims to solve, what concept underlies the project, what objectives will be accomplished, what actions will be taken, and who are the project's collaborators. Additionally, it must elucidate the "Why" behind the project's significance within the field of science and within your institution.

The excellence section, particularly concise and to-the-point introductions, essentially revolves around narrating the project's story.

It means that applicants should in their proposal/projects write **motivation** for the project – **why is this project idea important? What is the problem consortium will try to solve? Why is it important to solve it now?**

3.1 Objectives

From template:

- Briefly describe the objectives of your proposed work. Why are they pertinent to the work programme topic? Are they measurable and verifiable? Are they realistically achievable?
- Describe how your project goes beyond the state-of-the-art, and the extent the proposed work is ambitious. Indicate any exceptional ground-breaking R&I, novel concepts and approaches, new products, services or business and organisational models. Where relevant, illustrate the advance by referring to products and services already available on the market. Refer to any patent or publication search carried out.
- Describe where the proposed work is positioned in terms of R&I maturity (i.e. where it is situated in the spectrum from 'idea to application', or from 'lab to market'). Where applicable, provide an indication of the Technology Readiness Level, if possible distinguishing the start and by the end of the project.

Our recommendations:

- The scope of the topic or call is essential to consider. Project objectives should align with and be grounded in the precise boundaries, emphasis, and terminology of the given topic. Applicants must grasp the goals of the call and the work program and translate them into project objectives using consistent terminology. If relevant, these objectives should also be linked to EU policies mentioned earlier.
- Successful projects present their project concept, goals, or objectives prominently at the beginning.
- For example, “The main objective(s) of this project is/are ...” is a great way to start.
- Avoid employing identical words and terminology consistently; instead, strive for varied and engaging language to maintain the evaluator's interest.
- Include specific objectives (related to call topic):
 - These objectives should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) within the duration of the project.
 - These specific objectives have to be in line with expected outcomes and expected impacts.
 - These specific objectives should be quantifiable - e, i.e. each objective has to have a KPI. Key Performance Indicators facilitate the assessment of the project's overall performance.
 - These objectives have to be different from the operational & technical objectives, which are in the work-packages in section 3.

3.2 Coordination and/or support measures and methodology

From template:

- Describe and explain the overall methodology, including the concepts, models and assumptions that underpin your work. Explain how this will enable you to deliver your project's objectives. Refer to any important challenges you may have identified in the chosen methodology and how you intend to overcome them. *[e.g. 10 pages]*
- Describe any national or international research and innovation activities whose results will feed into the project, and how that link will be established; *[e.g. 1 page]*
- Explain how expertise and methods from different disciplines will be brought together and integrated in pursuit of your objectives. If you consider that an inter-disciplinary approach is unnecessary in the context of the proposed work, please provide a justification. *[e.g. 1/2 page]*
- For topics where the work programme indicates the need for the integration of social sciences and humanities, show the role of these disciplines in the project or provide a justification if you consider that these disciplines are not relevant to your proposed project. *[e.g. 1/2 page]*

- Describe how the gender dimension (i.e. sex and/or gender analysis) is taken into account in the project's research and innovation content [e.g. 1 page]. If you do not consider such a gender dimension to be relevant in your project, please provide a justification.
- Describe how appropriate open science practices are implemented as an integral part of the proposed methodology. Show how the choice of practices and their implementation are adapted to the nature of your work, in a way that will increase the chances of the project delivering on its objectives [e.g. 1 page]. If you believe that none of these practices are appropriate for your project, please provide a justification here.

Our recommendations:

This section is all about “how” and relates to the project idea, approach and methodology. In what way will the chosen methodology support the attainment of objectives and the delivery of results?

- The project's fundamental concept, including its primary concepts, models, assumptions, and related aspects, should be outlined and thoroughly explained. This subsection should vividly showcase the project's uniqueness. If similar endeavors exist, applicants must elucidate why the European Commission (EC) should financially support it. Furthermore, applicants should offer scientific justification for their proposed concept or idea to demonstrate their expertise to the evaluators.
- Answer to the question: How will the team achieve the aims/objectives? What steps need to be taken?
- It is advised to present an overall work plan of a project and explain the reason behind this approach.
- Explain the scientific methods, models and assumptions which underpin proposed work in the project.
- Mention the innovative aspects of a project presented in section above.
- Interdisciplinarity. Applicants need to describe how the elements and expertise from different disciplines will be used in the project in a complementary and comprehensive way.

What else not to underestimate:

- A description of the **experiences and reasons** that led to the selection of the given consortium participants.
- Research data management - specific, linked to goals, convincing, KPIs for measuring its compliance, FAIR principles - findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable.
- Open science.
- Gender equality (not only GEP, but also specific application of gender equality).

4. Impact

From template:

Impact – aspects to be taken into account.

- Credibility of the pathways to achieve the expected outcomes and impacts specified in the work programme, and the likely scale and significance of the contributions due to the project.
- Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities.

Our recommendations:

Horizon Europe is a framework program geared towards achieving meaningful outcomes. This emphasis has led to the introduction of new Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) and a modernized approach to monitoring and evaluating the program. This evaluation will gauge the success of Horizon Europe based on nine key narratives (KIPs) that fall into three categories: scientific, societal, and technological/economic impacts.

This section of your proposal should illustrate the short, medium, and long-term value that the project will create and how it will be accomplished (the pathways to value creation)? How widespread will the value be? How significant will the benefits be?

Evaluation criteria in the evaluation sheet:

Credibility of the pathways to achieve the expected outcomes and impacts specified in the work programme, and likely scale and significance of the contribution due to the project.

Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities

The most important elements of the chapter according to the ESR analysis:

- pathways aimed at achieving the expected outcomes and impacts
- barriers and obstacles to their achievement
- communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

The impact section is split in two main parts:

4.1 Project's pathways towards impacts

From template:

- Provide a **narrative** explaining how the project's results are expected to make a difference in terms of impact, beyond the immediate scope and duration of the project. The narrative should include the components below, tailored to your project.

Our recommendations:

- Ways to achieve the expected impact (specifically for each defined impact, supported by specific measures, ideally measurable).
- The description of pathways can also take the form of an action plan aimed at achieving short-term, medium-term and long-term outputs and impacts of the project.
- Applicant need to link their project objectives with expected impacts (described in WP/ Destination – long-term impacts that go beyond the project duration).
- These measurements should be quantified, grounded in a benchmark of sorts, and provided with precise definitions. After describing project contribution to wider impacts, applicants have to link their project objectives to expected outcomes (identified in the call text – short to medium term, 2-5 years), and again identified expected outcomes have to be quantified and benchmark explained.
- Explain how great (reaching different stakeholder groups, geographical reach) of a change the project effects will have (scale) and how important they will be (significance).
- It is important to have clearly identified SMART KPIs and clear project specific targeted groups.

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4.2 Measures to maximise impact – Dissemination, exploitation and communication

From template:

- Describe the planned measures to maximise the impact of your project by providing a first version of your 'plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities'. Describe the dissemination, exploitation and communication measures that are planned, and the target group(s) addressed (e.g. scientific community, end users, financial actors, public at large).
- Outline your strategy for the management of intellectual property, foreseen protection measures, such as patents, design rights, copyright, trade secrets, etc., and how these would be used to support

Our recommendations:

Communication tools and proposed activities must be described for each proposed activity in the Excellence chapter and for outputs and impacts described in the Impact chapter.

Consider different target groups.

The communication and dissemination plan should include:

- what (what information and, outputs, impacts...) will be communicated;
- who (don't leave it to just 1 consortium participant);
- to whom (target groups, their justification);
- how (description of means/tools by which information will be communicated to individual target groups);
- when;
- outputs;
- indicators.

The proposed strategy/plan can be presented in a table format which explains the communication strategy used, proposed actions, evidencing the targets of communication and the quality of dissemination during the lifetime of the project and beyond. As for example:

Targeted groups	Means of reaching those targeted groups	Outcomes	Indicators and targets
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What else not to underestimate:

- Involvement of citizens in projects (one of the target groups), or involving different types of institutions (public, private, ...).
- Sustainability of the project even after the end of financing from the EK.
- Design and implementation of joint exploitation measures at the level of the project as a whole (not their implementation by individual project partners separately).

5. Quality and efficiency of the implementation

The detailed work plan presented in this section becomes a contractual obligation that must be thoroughly executed once the project is funded, hence this section needs attention and time to be written properly.

From template:

Quality and efficiency of the implementation – aspects to be taken into account

- Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks, and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages, and the resources overall*
- Capacity and role of each participant, and extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise.*

Our recommendations:

This section (around 10 pages, including tables) will be composed of different work packages (WPs) and activities, which will have to be coherent, clearly understood and read as one voice. There is a practice to ask different partners to write WPs they are responsible for, however, there is a danger that “one voice” could be lost and the implementation plan would become incoherent. It is better to have few meetings with partners before starting with creating work packages and to ask the partners to present you their capabilities, capacities, needs and expectations from the project. This way the coordinator will be able to create coherent WPs that have logic and flow. Applicants should present an overall work plan overview in this section before listing each WP separately, this will give an overview for the evaluators. This can be done via PERT diagram or some other graphical representation.

Evaluation criteria in the evaluation sheet:

Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks, and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work package, and the resources overall.

Capacity and role of each participant, and extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise.

The most important elements of the chapter according to the ESR analysis:

- structure and interconnection of WPs and tasks and properly set milestones and deliverables;
- expertise and experience of consortium members to implement the proposed WPs;
- risks related to implementation.

5.1 Work plan and resources

The WPs structure, during the evaluation phase, enables the experts reviewing the application to assess the work involved in the project in terms of logic, relevance, collaboration, coherence, effectiveness, competitiveness, innovation, etc. More importantly – the WPs presentation is in fact a primary justification for the requested grant. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to make it as competitive as possible (while still possible for execution). It is imperative that applicants develop the project idea/concept first and only afterwards define the WPs, which in turn will derive from the project's objectives. Concept, Objectives, Task to achieve those objectives (WPs). Partners can provide an input and feedback, but the writing and ownership should be by one person.

From template:

Please provide the following:

- brief presentation of the overall structure of the work plan;
- timing of the different work packages and their components (Gantt chart or similar);
- graphical presentation of the components showing how they inter-relate (Pert chart or similar).
- detailed work description, i.e.:
 - a list of work packages (table 3.1a);
 - a description of each work package (table 3.1b);
 - a list of deliverables (table 3.1c);
- a list of milestones (table 3.1d);
- a list of critical risks, relating to project implementation, that the stated project's objectives may not be achieved. Detail any risk mitigation measures. You will be able to update the list of critical risks and mitigation measures as the project progresses (table 3.1e);
- a table showing number of person months required (table 3.1f);
- a table showing description and justification of subcontracting costs for each participant (table 3.1g);
- a table showing justifications for 'purchase costs' (table 3.1h) for participants where those costs exceed 15% of the personnel costs (according to the budget table in proposal part A);
- if applicable, a table showing justifications for 'other costs categories' (table 3.1i);
- if applicable, a table showing in-kind contributions from third parties (table 3.1j)

Our recommendations:

- The coordinator ought to request partners to furnish the following information: an assessment of the time and resources required for each task, going beyond the work package level as outlined in the official proposal template. This should include

a breakdown of person-months allocated to each task and partner, along with any related expenses.

- All partners need to agree on timeline on various tasks and how each task complements each other.
- Avoid allocating more than 40% of the overall budget to a single country (all partners from the same country put together, however, this does not apply to Widening coordinator).
- The budget allocated for coordination and project management activities (mostly by the coordinator) should be in range between 3% and 5.5% of the overall budget.
- WPs must be logically linked and in perfect harmony with project goals, outcomes, expected impact and D&E activities.
- Mandatory WPs are Project management and Dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.
- Milestones are certain significant events in the project (end of stage, etc.), max 5 per 1 project, e.g. completion of technology development – prototype.
- Deliverables prove the fulfilment of the set goals, max 2-3 per 1 WPs, e.g. technical documentation for the prototype, developed study materials, standardized work procedure, summary of conference outputs.

5.2 Capacity of participants and consortium as a whole

From template:

- Describe the consortium. How does it match the project's objectives, and bring together the necessary disciplinary and inter-disciplinary knowledge? Show how this includes expertise in social sciences and humanities, open science practices, and gender aspects of R&I, as appropriate. Include in the description affiliated entities and associated partners, if any.
- Show how the partners will have access to critical infrastructure needed to carry out the project activities.
- Describe how the members complement one another (and cover the value chain, where appropriate)
- In what way does each of them contribute to the project? Show that each has a valid role, and adequate resources in the project to fulfil that role.
- If applicable, describe the industrial/commercial involvement in the project to ensure exploitation of the results and explain why this is consistent with and will help to achieve the specific measures which are proposed for exploitation of the results of the project (see section 2.2).

- **Other countries and international organisations:** If one or more of the participants requesting EU funding is based in a country or is an international organisation that is not automatically eligible for such funding (entities from Member States of the EU, from Associated Countries and from one of the countries in the exhaustive list included in the Work Programme General Annexes B are automatically eligible for EU funding), explain why the participation of the entity in question is essential to successfully carry out the project.

Our recommendations:

- Describe the consortium. How does it match the project’s objectives, and bring together the necessary disciplinary and inter-disciplinary knowledge? Show how this includes expertise in social sciences and humanities, open science practices, and gender aspects of R&I.
- Include in the description affiliated entities and associated partners.
- Show how the partners will have access to critical infrastructure needed to carry out the project activities.
- In what way does each of them contribute to the project?
- Describe the industrial/ commercial involvement in the project.
- Not in general about UNI, but precisely linked things to specific work. Packages and members appearing in them, relevant to the requirements of the call.
- It's not that we have it ready and put it into all projects.
- Complementarity – all specific objectives are covered by consortium members.
- Description of interdisciplinarity.

From template:

Table 3.1e:

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures

Our recommendations:

Add obstacles and project perspective, e.g. problems with implementation, insufficient funds, problems with public procurement.

From template:

Table 3.1h:

Participant Number/Short Name		
	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence		
Equipment		
Other goods, works and services		
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total		

Our recommendations:

Add very specific justifications. Be concrete, e.g. 3 foreign business trips per 2 experts per 3 days – 1800 €, participation in the conference (3 confer., for 5 people), study stay (1), ...